

Evaluating the role of Homeopathic medicine Testosterone in its various attenuations for its anti-cancer activity on Breast Cancer cell line MCF-7.

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ABSTRACT

The second most prevalent type of cancer which is also the leading cause of women death in India is Breast Cancer. In its treatment several recommendation and measures are considered. Androgen receptors have been found on breast cancer cell lines and testosterone has been used as hormone therapy against breast cancer. Homeopathic medicines are part of complementary and alternative medicines are used for the treatment of cancer. The objective of the study is to investigate and evaluate the anticancer activity of commercially available homeopathic preparations of Testosterone. To test the viability of breast cancer (MCF-7) cell line, 3-(4,5-Dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT) assay was conducted with negative control, ethanol and various attenuations of homeopathic medicine Testosterone at 24 hours. Ethanol was tested to be safe to the cells up to 3µl thereby coherent to the cells being viable up to 3% of alcohol. Multiple comparisons between tested reagents at different concentrations confirmed the significance of the said results. At concentration of 1:33, 6CH and 200CH potency shows superior activity in comparison to negative control, ethanol, 30CH and 1M potency ($p < 0.001$). These preliminary significant results warrant further *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies to evaluate the potential of Testosterone as a medicine to treat breast cancer.

Keywords: Homeopathy, Breast cancer, Testosterone, *in vitro*, Anticancer activity.

INTRODUCTION

Breast cancer is the second leading cause of cancer death in women worldwide and ranks as the first leading cause of death in India⁽¹⁻³⁾. The treatments that are given to breast cancer patients generally include chemotherapy, radiotherapy and/or several hormone therapies⁽⁴⁾. Targeted therapies for breast cancer embark on the biomarkers estrogen receptor (ER), progesterone receptor (PR), and human epidermal growth factor receptor type 2 (Her2); however, there are triple-negative (ER/PR/Her2-negative) tumors, that fail to express these three markers thereby limiting the treatment strategies for patients. The androgen receptors (AR) are also expressed in up to 90% of the breast cancers with a frequency comparable to or higher than ER or PR.⁽⁵⁻⁷⁾ The endogenous androgen metabolism play an important role in the development of breast cancer⁽⁸⁾. With the evident role of AR the use of Testosterone as a therapeutic agent with beneficial results have been well established.^(6,9,10) These modes of treatment are often painful and are associated with considerable side effects. It inhibits bone marrow stem cell proliferation leading to immune suppression. Radiotherapy affects the lymphocytes resulting in prolonged T-cell

suppression. Other side effects includes bone necrosis, nausea, lung fibrosis, skin

devascularization, ulceration, vomiting, and renal damage are also associated with all types of conventional therapies. People often look for other modes of treatment that have relatively fewer or no side effects and can complement the ongoing treatment.⁽¹¹⁾ Homeopathy is one such arm of complementary and alternative therapy that causes the patient no pain and has no or negligible side effects with use⁽¹²⁾. Homeopathic medicines are made up of natural products and are a highly diluted preparation which decreases the side effects and increases the effectivity of the drugs. Homeopathic practitioners use mother tinctures, as well as potentized remedies diluted to both below and above Avogadro's limit depending on the patient's condition, and claim to find all remedies effective against the disease symptoms for a given condition. Meta-analysis of various clinical trials have found the effectiveness of ultra-high diluted homeopathic medicines^(13,14). Incidentally, many earlier reports have recorded efficacy of both the lower and the higher potencies of homeopathic remedies in hepatic and breast cancer studies^(15,16). A meta-analysis states that

homeopathic medicines are effective as an adjuvant, in the treatment of cancer.(17) Hormone treatment incorporates the use of estrogen, progesterone, testosterone along with allied components. There are similar medicinal compounds in CAM treatment. Testosterone is also commercially available homeopathic medicine used in several medications. Homeopathic testosterone allows the body to re-balance without side effects. The potencies that are commercially available are 6CH, 30CH,

200CH, 1M etc. in which 6CH potency refers to 1:10¹², 30CH is 1:10⁶⁰, 200CH is 1:10⁴⁰⁰ and 1M is 1:10²⁰⁰⁰ of the basic medicinal source element(18).For the first time, effect of various homeopathic preparations of Testosterone was evaluated for the viability of breast cancer (MCF-7) cell line, in the present study. In control, ethanol was also taken into consideration to rule out the role of alcohol which is used as the medium for homeopathic medicines.

Figure 1: The effect of control, ethanol and homeopathic preparations on cell viability at different concentrations from 0.5µl to 5µl expressed as Mean ± SEM.

The homeopathic preparations of Testosterone were diluted in MEM as concentration of 0.5µl to 5µl which were all same to that of ethanol. The potency that has shown the effect on the breast cancer cell line is 30CH and 200CH from dilutions 3µl to 4.5µl. For 1M potency it has shown at 5µl. However, at lower or higher dilutions cells were viable as in control. Thus homeopathic preparations of 30CH, 200CH & 1M exhibited anticancer activity against breast cancer cells (Figure 2). It was observed that at 24 hours, all the potencies significantly reduced the growth kinetics, more significantly at 3µl as compared to other dilutions, ethanol as well as untreated control cells.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Homeopathic Samples

Homeopathic preparations of Testosterone [6CH, 30CH, 200CH and 1M] was procured from GMP certified St. George's Homoeopathic Pharmacy & Extra Neutral Alcohol (ENA) 95% v/v was commercially bought.

Cell Culture

The cell line MCF-7 was obtained from American Type Culture Collection (ATCC), Mumbai, India. The cells were grown in MEM (Minimum Essential

Medium Eagle) supplemented with L-glutamine, Sodium Bicarbonate (7.5%), Penicillin & Streptomycin, and 10% Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS) and were incubated in a humidified 5% CO₂ incubator at 37°C. MCF-7 is estrogen & progesterone positive cell line & highly sensitive.

Reagents & Plastic ware

MEM, L-glutamine, Sodium Bicarbonate (7.5%), Penicillin & Streptomycin, FBS, Phosphate Buffer Saline (PBS), Trypsin Phosphate Versene Glucose (TPVG), 3-(4,5-Dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT) dye (50 mg/ml), Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), Glycine buffer (0.1M glycine, 0.1M NaCl, pH adjusted to 10.5 by adding 1N NaOH) were used in this experiment.

25cm² Cell Culture Flasks, 96-well plates, Sterile Tips & Micropipettes, 100-1000ml flasks, Test-tube Stand & Measuring cylinder were used.

Drug Preparation

For cell culture experiments, each potency (6CH, 30CH, 200CH and 1M) was diluted in MEM as concentration of drug being from 0.5µl to 5µl per 100µl. In 350µl thereby the each concentration was

3.5x and rest completed by MEM to make up 350µl solution.

MTT Assay (Methylthiazolyldiphenyl-tetrazolium bromide)

The cytotoxicity assay was performed as single blinded experiment on MCF-7 cell line with the homeopathic drug testosterone of 6CH, 30CH, 200CH and 1M with concentration of drug 0.5µl to 5µl for all the potencies. Ethanol was also evaluated for its effect on cells with the same dilutions as the drugs. Approximately, 1×10^4 were grown in triplicates in 96-well plates for 24 hours and then treated with different concentration & kept for incubation for 24 hours. To determine Cell viability, 10µl MTT dye was added in dark & sterile conditions and kept for incubation for 3 hours at 37°C. After incubation, media was removed & 100µl of DMSO was added. The plates were incubated for 10 minutes followed by addition of glycine buffer. The purple formazan was determined by measuring OD (optical density) at 550 nm by an Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA) plate reader.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The significances of differences between data of control and drugs treated MCF-7 cells were statistical analyzed for data was performed with Two-Factor Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) with the help of

statistical analysis software GraphPad Prism 7. All quantitative analysis data were obtained from representative experiments with triplicate and were expressed as Mean ± Standard Error of Mean (SEM).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Experiments earlier have proven that there was growth inhibition using testosterone in MCF-7 cells.(9) The mechanism of inhibitory activity of testosterone is complex, either the effect of estrogen is opposed on tumor growth or by other means which needs more detailed study.(19)

Effect of homeopathic preparations of Testosterone on the viability of breast cancer cells

The test was to examine whether the drug will reduce the viability of breast cancer cells. Since all the attenuation contained ethanol as its solvent, we initially tested the effect of ethanol on breast cancer (MCF-7) cells. The cells were treated with concentration of extra neutral alcohol (0.5µl to 5µl). Ethanol was tested to be safe to the cells up to 3µl thereby coherent to the fact that cells are only viable up to 3% of alcohol (Figure 1). The tests were conducted with medium alone, extra neutral alcohol and various attenuations of homeopathic medicine Testosterone at 24 hours.

Figure 2: The mean effect of control, ethanol and homeopathic medicine on cell viability.

The remedy was selected to be Testosterone on the grounds of hormone therapy using testosterone as its

remedial measure.(19) There are evidence proving that MCF-7, the breast cancer cell line, expresses the

androgen receptor. The role of testosterone and DHT in inhibiting the cell proliferation in these cell lines is also documented. This underlines the significance of androgens in breast cancer development. For the first time, homeopathic Testosterone was used to prove its effect on breast cancer. The results of homeopathic Testosterone proved that the action was not that of alcohol, which is used a solvent, but of the medicine itself. The tests were performed in triplicates using negative control, ethanol as the solvent control and the various attenuations of homeopathic

medicine Testosterone. The treatment with ethanol was safe up to 3 μ l which indicated that the controls and the tested remedy compared at 3 μ l showed maximum resemblance to the genuine results on cancer cells. The data of the OD measured at 550 nm was measured at the end of 24 hours. It is expressed as Mean \pm SEM in Table 1. The concentration from 0.5 μ l to 5 μ l is of concentration ratio of 1:200, 1:100, 1:67, 1:50, 1:33, 1:28, 1:25, 1:22 and 1:20 respectively.

Table 1: Effect of the control, alcohol and homeopathic preparations of Testosterone on cell viability of MCF-7. The table shows number of viable cells $\times 10^4$ represented as Mean \pm SEM of three independent experiments. $p < 0.001$ indicates statistically significant differences compared to the control untreated group.

Concentration	Control	Alcohol	6CH	30CH	200CH	1M
1:200	0.966 \pm 0.018	1.131 \pm 0.040	1.039 \pm 0.004	1.140 \pm 0.105	1.164 \pm 0.079	1.098 \pm 0.071
1:100	1.05 \pm 0.088	0.975 \pm 0.293	1.109 \pm 0.066	1.195 \pm 0.132	1.293 \pm 0.140	1.031 \pm 0.045
1:67	1.311 \pm 0.034	1.005 \pm 0.031	1.075 \pm 0.039	1.069 \pm 0.083	1.143 \pm 0.083	0.893 \pm 0.053
1:50	1.329 \pm 0.065	1.138 \pm 0.126	0.965 \pm 0.045	1.042 \pm 0.913	1.161 \pm 0.114	1.071 \pm 0.098
1:33	1.003 \pm 0.030	0.909 \pm 0.045	0.510 \pm 0.051	0.842 \pm 0.039	0.374 \pm 0.006	1.005 \pm 0.108
1:28	1.019 \pm 0.022	0.684 \pm 0.047	0.390 \pm 0.058	0.582 \pm 0.006	0.297 \pm 0.014	0.631 \pm 0.056
1:25	0.967 \pm 0.034	0.593 \pm 0.064	0.392 \pm 0.066	0.392 \pm 0.007	0.228 \pm 0.002	0.440 \pm 0.025
1:22	0.949 \pm 0.029	0.459 \pm 0.070	0.333 \pm 0.080	0.310 \pm 0.004	0.216 \pm 0.013	0.376 \pm 0.034
1:20	1.025 \pm 0.018	0.097 \pm 0.006	0.053 \pm 0.001	0.063 \pm 0.002	0.057 \pm 0.002	0.055 \pm 0.001

Multiple comparisons between negative control, ethanol and various potencies at different concentrations were done in order to understand the significance of the said results.

Table 2: Multiple comparison test between Control, Alcohol, Potencies at concentration of 1:100, 1:67, 1:50 and 1:33 respectively

Tukey's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Summary	Adjusted P Value
1:100				
Alcohol vs. 200CH	-0.3183	-0.5688 to -0.06787	**	0.0048
200CH vs. 1M	0.2623	0.01187 to 0.5128	*	0.0345
1:67				
Control vs. 1M	0.418	0.1675 to 0.6685	****	<0.0001
1:50				
Control vs. 6CH	0.3643	0.1139 to 0.6148	***	0.0008
Control vs. 30CH	0.2873	0.03687 to 0.5378	*	0.0150
Control vs. 1M	0.2583	0.007868 to 0.5088	*	0.0392
1:33				
Control vs. 6CH	0.4933	0.2429 to 0.7438	****	<0.0001
Control vs. 200CH	0.63	0.3795 to 0.8805	****	<0.0001
Alcohol vs. 6CH	0.3993	0.1489 to 0.6498	***	0.0002
Alcohol vs. 200CH	0.536	0.2855 to 0.7865	****	<0.0001
6CH vs. 30CH	-0.3313	-0.5818 to -0.08087	**	0.0029
6CH vs. 1M	-0.495	-0.7455 to -0.2445	****	<0.0001
30CH vs. 200CH	0.468	0.2175 to 0.7185	****	<0.0001
200CH vs. 1M	-0.6317	-0.8821 to -0.3812	****	<0.0001

Table 2 depicts the data of the multiple comparison sets at concentration of 1:100, 1:67, 1:50 and 1:33. At 1:100, surprisingly, the activity of 200CH potency is effective with significant $p < 0.05$ against ethanol as well as 1M potency. 1:67 did not show substantial results as only 1M proved to be significant compared to negative control. At concentration level of 1:50

potencies showed significant activity against negative control only, thereby not of major importance. However at 1:33, 6CH shows considerable activity against negative control, ethanol, 30CH and 1M potency ($p < 0.001$). 200CH potency showed superior activity in comparison to negative control, ethanol, 30CH and 1M potency ($p < 0.001$).

Table 3: Multiple comparison test between Control, Alcohol, Potencies at concentration of 1:28.

Tukey's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Summary	Adjusted P Value
3.5μl				
Control vs. Alcohol	0.3347	0.0842 to 0.5851	**	0.0026
Control vs. 6CH	0.628	0.3775 to 0.8785	****	<0.0001
Control vs. 30CH	0.4363	0.1859 to 0.6868	****	<0.0001
Control vs. 200CH	0.7213	0.4709 to 0.9718	****	<0.0001
Control vs. 1M	0.3877	0.1372 to 0.6381	***	0.0003
Alcohol vs. 6CH	0.2933	0.04287 to 0.5438	*	0.0121
Alcohol vs. 200CH	0.3867	0.1362 to 0.6371	***	0.0003
30CH vs. 200CH	0.285	0.03453 to 0.5355	*	0.0162
200CH vs. 1M	-0.3337	-0.5841 to -0.0832	**	0.0027
Control vs. 200CH	0.739	0.4885 to 0.9895	****	<0.0001
Control vs. 1M	0.527	0.2765 to 0.7775	****	<0.0001
Alcohol vs. 200CH	0.365	0.1145 to 0.6155	***	0.0007

Table 3 narrates the multiple comparison between the activities of negative control, ethanol and all attenuations at 1:28. 6CH potency was statistically significant in comparison to negative control and ethanol ($p < 0.001$ and $p = 0.01$), whereas 30CH only showed good activity against the negative control. 200CH potency showed par results when compared to that of negative control, ethanol, 30CH and 1M potency ($p < 0.001$).

Table 4: Multiple comparison test between Control, Alcohol, Potencies at concentration of 1:25, 1:22 and 1:20 respectively.

Tukey's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Summary	Adjusted P Value
4μl				
Control vs. Alcohol	0.374	0.1235 to 0.6245	***	0.0005
Control vs. 6CH	0.575	0.3245 to 0.8255	****	<0.0001
Control vs. 30CH	0.575	0.3245 to 0.8255	****	<0.0001
4.5μl				
Control vs. Alcohol	0.489	0.2385 to 0.7395	****	<0.0001
Control vs. 6CH	0.6157	0.3652 to 0.8661	****	<0.0001
Control vs. 30CH	0.6383	0.3879 to 0.8888	****	<0.0001
Control vs. 200CH	0.733	0.4825 to 0.9835	****	<0.0001
Control vs. 1M	0.5727	0.3222 to 0.8231	****	<0.0001
5μl				
Control vs. Alcohol	0.928	0.6775 to 1.178	****	<0.0001
Control vs. 6CH	0.9717	0.7212 to 1.222	****	<0.0001
Control vs. 30CH	0.962	0.7115 to 1.212	****	<0.0001
Control vs. 200CH	0.968	0.7175 to 1.218	****	<0.0001
Control vs. 1M	0.9697	0.7192 to 1.22	****	<0.0001

Table 4 describes the results of the multiple comparison sets at concentration of 1:25, 1:22 and 1:20 respectively. All the result analysis for the said concentration only portrays that the remedies and

ethanol were only significant against negative control and not between themselves. This depicts that cell viability is poor on account of alcohol interference.

Conclusion

This exploratory study evaluated the anticancer activity of testosterone against breast cancer cell line. Almost all the potencies exhibited anticancer activity but 6CH and 200CH has significantly shown the major effect on the cell line. According to the Statistical Analysis the data is proven to be significant. This result can help to further explore this activity by use of tests like FACS (Fluorescent Activated Cell Sorting), Fluorescent Microscopy, etc. All the appropriate measures were taken into consideration for this experiment and results are significant to go for further processing. This preliminary data gives evidences for further depth *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies for establishing the effective potencies that could hold promising results in the treatment for breast cancer.

Conflict of Interest

The authors bare no conflict of interest in the above study.

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